

SCHOOL ADMINISTRATORS' LEADERSHIP STYLES AND MANAGEMENT SKILLS IN RELATION TO HEALTH CRISIS RESPONSE AMONG PRIVATE TERTIARY INSTITUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed to determine the leadership styles and management skills used by the school administrators in private tertiary educational institutions in Dipolog City, Philippines in relation to health crisis response. A descriptive correlational design was used to analyze data from one hundred eleven respondents using a convenient sampling technique. The gathered information underwent analysis using *Mean and Standard Deviation, Pearson Correlation Coefficient, and Stepwise Regression Analysis*. The findings showed that the school administrators very highly used laissez-faire, transformational, democratic, and transactional leadership styles, while laissez-faire was chiefly used during the health crisis. Conceptual, interpersonal, and technological skills were very highly used in managing the health crisis. Conceptual skills were used predominantly. The school administrators very highly responded to enrollment, staffing, physical set-up, facility changes, and teaching modality used. The style of leadership of administrators positively correlates with their responses to the crisis in enrollment, staffing, physical set-up facility changes, and teaching modality but shows negative correlations with autocratic leadership as to staffing and teaching modality. The administrators' management skills significantly influenced their response to the health crisis. Transactional and democratic leadership and conceptual management skills were identified as predictors of administrators' response to the health crisis. In conclusion, laissez-faire leadership and conceptual management skills were predominantly used; transactional and democratic leaderships and conceptual management skills played a significant role in shaping administrators' response, while responding very highly to enrolment.

Keywords: *crisis, leadership, management, response, skills*

INTRODUCTION

A crisis is an extraordinary situation that suddenly appears over time, which puts organizations in trouble (Tokel et al, 2017). It may disrupts businesses, cause economic loss, and greatly impacts education, leaving school administrators uncertain. The role of school administrators becomes crucial during a health crisis as they make decisions to prevent school shutdowns. Thus, they need to respond rapidly and adaptively. The traits and behaviors of leaders have been found to play a significant role in crises (Caringal-Go et al., 2021). Leaders use different styles of leadership and management, though they often suddenly change in crises (Ali and Anwar 2021; Purnomo et al., 2021; Bagwell, 2020). Charismatic leadership was impactful in crisis management in Iraq (Ali and Anwar, 2021). In challenging environments, transformational leadership was identified as the most suitable style (Mathende and Yousefi, 2021), and research showed the positive effects of transformational, transactional, and charismatic leadership on crisis management (Purnomo et al., 2021). Effective leadership during a health crisis includes attending to individuals, assuming responsibility, providing guidance, and maintaining morale (Smith, 2021).

Management is the core of an organization; its success depends on how management is done (Das, 2023). Effective crisis management requires administrators to assume responsibility for organizational plans, actions, and decisions (Leta and Chan, 2021). Leveraging technology, managerial knowledge, and capabilities in utilizing information is crucial for quality management during crises (Simeunović et al., 2019). Studies have shown that integrating the three management skills identified by Katz (conceptual, technical, and human) is important for effective leadership (Jaqua and Jaqua, 2021), and the application of these skills influences school effectiveness (Mukarromah et al., 2019). Technical skills help acquire proficiency in work; it is the ability to use appropriate tools and techniques. Conceptual skills enable a manager to work with ideas and concepts, such as formulating organizational goals. Managers also require human skills that enable them to work with people to achieve a common goal through cooperation and understanding people's needs when making decisions affecting them. Human skills are vital due to managers' frequent interactions with staff at different operational levels (Cornell, 2019). Successful crisis management relies on technical, conceptual, and human skills, adaptability, and the utilization of technology and information (Cornell, 2019).

During a health crises, effective crisis response relies on the leadership styles and management skills of school administrators. DeMartino and Weiser (2021) highlight the importance of communication, care, trust, and agency in crises, emphasizing the need for agile and proactive leadership. Employee safety is also crucial (Luceño-Moreno et al., 2020), and health-oriented leadership behavior can protect organizations (Klebe et al., 2021). Kim's (2021) research identifies clear communication, collaboration, information

sharing, decision-making, appropriate prioritization, and building trust and competency as key attributes of crisis leadership.

Recent studies have examined the role of school leadership and management during a health crisis. Pounder (2021) investigated the impact of different leadership styles on crisis management, exploring how these styles influence administrators' ability to respond to health crises effectively. It was found that a responsible leadership approach to facing a crisis is a way of looking at the issue in a positive way, producing opportunities for progress and change, such as emphasizing commitment to the common good, providing constructive societal impact, and navigating uncertainties during a health crisis can provide hope for plans. Brown et al. (2023) specifically examine the experiences of school administrators during a health crisis, and identify effective crisis leadership practices, such as resilient and responsive styles of leadership, by connecting and supporting all members of the school community to address equity through building staff and students' capacity to respond to changes such as digital and technological changes, decision-making and communication strategies.

In the study of do Lago et al. (2023) about the strategies of higher educational institutions during the COVID-19 pandemic, maintaining the continuity of learning in the classroom remotely to maintain the financial stability of the institutions by responding to the concerns of stakeholders was one of the strategies they found that the schools used. Training teachers to maintain the quality of teaching in a remote environment was one of the best possible responses the school administrators used in response to the challenges that arise do Lago et al. (2023).

Private higher educational institutions are also greatly affected by the drastic changes brought by the health crisis in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. Nationwide, all schools were mandated by the Commission on Higher Education (CHED, 2020) to switch to flexible teaching-learning activities using modules and online, and then later switch to limited face-to-face learning modality while implementing the health and safety protocols mandated by the CHED, DOH, IATF, and the LGU. Tertiary private schools in Dipolog City try ways to comply with what this CHED mandates for all tertiary schools, such as the use of masks, alcohol, hand hygiene, and social distancing.

This set-up put much pressure on the leadership and management of school administrators, given the skills of faculty in a new mode of student learning, technology to use for teaching and learning, internet connection, which is very weak in this city, and constraint financial budget due to the decreasing number of enrollees. Financial and resource constraints brought by this health crisis are also a challenge. How the school administrators address the issues from the start of the pandemic, the peak of the pandemic, up to the gradual return to normalcy are concerns of this study.

There are literature and studies on crisis leadership and management in varying organizations; however, there are few recent literature and studies focusing on private tertiary education and health crisis situations. Most studies were conducted in basic education in public institutions and in other entrepreneurial businesses. Thus, the

literature on school administrators' leadership and management in crisis response needs to be expanded, highlighting a research gap. While there is a growing body of research on crisis management and leadership in general, more recent studies need to focus specifically on the strategies employed by school administrators during a crisis situation particularly a health crisis. By exploring these aspects, this study contributes to filling the research gap by offering insights into effective leadership styles, management strategies, and crisis response practices.

The findings from these studies provide valuable knowledge for improving future crisis management in the education sector and have practical implications for school administrators, policymakers, and researchers. Further research in this area is necessary to enhance the understanding of school administrators' leadership and management practices in the context of crisis response and to provide guidance for effective crisis preparedness and response in the education sector for future use if there is a crisis that may occur again in the future.

Research Questions

This research aimed to determine the leadership styles and management skills used by the school administrators in private tertiary educational institutions in Dipolog City, Philippines in relation to a health crisis response.

1. What are the leadership styles used by the school administrators in terms of transactional leadership, transformational leadership, democratic leadership, laissez-faire leadership, and autocratic leadership?
2. What are the management skills used by the school administrators in terms of technical management skills, interpersonal management skills, and conceptual management skills?
3. What are the school administrators responses to a health crisis in terms of enrollment, staffing, physical set-up and facility changes, and teaching modality used?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the administrators' leadership styles and their responses to a health crisis?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the administrators' management skills and their responses to a health crisis?
6. What are the predictors of school administrators' health crisis response?

METHODOLOGY

This research used quantitative design to determine the leadership styles and management skills used by the school administrators in private tertiary educational institutions in Dipolog City, Zamboanga del Norte, Philippines in relation to crisis response. A descriptive correlational design was used to describe the administrators' responses to a crisis, and their leadership styles and management skills during the crisis. Descriptive design is used to identify and measure the variables and describe them, which

are the leadership styles, management skills, and their responses to a crisis. Correlational research was used in the quantitative research using research-made questionnaires to gather data from one hundred eleven school administrators. The respondents of this research were the faculty in the four private higher education institutions in Dipolog City who experienced drastic changes in the educational system due to a crisis. This research used a convenient sampling technique and took one hundred and eleven faculty members within the criteria of sampling. The researcher used a structured research-made questionnaire to determine the type of leadership of school administrators and the management skills they used and their response to a health crisis using a 4-point Likert Scale. A pilot test of the questionnaires was made and subjected to Cronbach's Alpha tests to measure the reliability of the research instrument first before gathering data from the respondents. The statistical tools used in this research were the *Average Weighted Mean and Standard Deviation, Pearson correlation coefficient (r) and Stepwise Regression Analysis*.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Respondents' Leadership Styles

Table 1 shows the *laissez-faire leadership style* with the highest weighted mean (WM=3.44; SD=0.5427). During the health crisis, school administrators predominantly used the *laissez-faire leadership style*, which the respondents very highly used. This approach gives autonomy to subordinates, allowing quick decisions based on expertise and local conditions to respond effectively to challenges. Laissez-faire leadership empowers individuals, fostering trust in teams during a crisis, where quick decision-making is crucial. Laissez-faire leadership was described by Ali et al. (2015) as a style of leadership that abdicates responsibility, delays decisions, and avoids taking stands on the issues concerned. Contrary to the findings of Ali et al. (2015), Kostianen (2023) stressed that decentralized decision-making allows quick responses at the local level, which is crucial in a crisis to avoid bureaucratic delays. Though characterized by a hands-off approach, laissez-faire minimizes micromanagement, enhancing job satisfaction and efficiency among staff. Tong (2020) found that Laissez-Faire psychological leadership has a positive effect on the learning ability of an organization. Oprea et al. (2022) stressed that this style of leadership may lead to positive job-crafting behaviors in subordinates. Andoh and Ghansah (2019) also stressed that Laissez-faire is an appropriate approach when employees clearly understand their responsibility and if the leader is undoubtedly confident in the abilities of team members. Okpokwasili and Kalu (2021) held that laissez-faire leadership can be used where creativity is highly encouraged. Suong et al. (2019) found that letting the workers make their own decisions is very significant in the academic environment.

The second most used leadership style by school administrators during the health crisis was *transformational leadership* (WM= 3.39; SD=0.5943), which shows the respondents used it very highly. Transformational leadership inspires and motivates employees with a clear vision, providing direction during the health crisis. Administrators opt for this style to

encourage creativity and adaptability, which are vital for finding innovative solutions. The focus on individual development supports staff needs, fosters care, and promotes team well-being. Prioritizing relationships and trust, transformational leaders enhance communication and collaboration, which are essential for navigating uncertainties (Shields and Hesbol, 2020). Schein and Schein (2018) highlighted that this leadership style contributes to a positive organizational culture, chosen by administrators to create an optimistic environment, motivating the school community during challenges. The study by Purwanto (2020) indicates that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on the ability of teachers to innovate. At the same time, Zaman et al. (2020) shows that transformational leadership has a positive and significant effect on readiness to change. The preference for transformational leadership as the second most used style indicates administrators' recognition of its importance in not only addressing immediate challenges but also cultivating a positive and adaptive culture, promoting innovation and collaboration among school staff during the health crisis.

The third most used leadership style by school administrators during the health crisis is *democratic leadership* (WM=3.37; SD=0.6594). This style of leadership is also very highly used by school administrators during a pandemic. Democratic leadership allows team members to be included in decisions and promotes collaboration. Administrators chose this style for a unified approach, ensuring collective support for decisions and shared responsibility in navigating crisis complexities. It allows flexibility and quick adaptability to changing situations, which is crucial during a health crisis. The inclusive decision-making process enables swift adjustments to emerging challenges. Democratic leadership positively impacts team morale by involving individuals and fostering ownership and commitment (Villegas, 2022). This boosts morale, contributing to overall team resilience amid a health crisis. By prioritizing open communication, democratic leaders ensure effective information flow during a crisis. Nabi et al. (2022) underscore that in the use of a democratic leadership style, administrators value collaboration, inclusivity, and consensus-building, which are essential for effective decision-making and maintaining a positive team environment in education. Tiwari and Singh (2021) state that most employees in managerial and supervisory positions during COVID-19 used the democratic style of leadership in various companies.

Transactional leadership ranks fourth among other leadership styles, (WM=3.34, SD=0.5427), indicating school administrators less favored it during the health crisis. However, on the continuum, it still falls under the very highly utilized leadership styles among the respondents. This style is known for its clear expectations and rewards/punishments approach, which is suitable for routine and stable environments. Purwanto (2020) shows that transactional leadership, together with transformational leadership, has positive and significant effects on teachers' ability to innovate. Transactional leadership motivates workers to perform at a higher level, exert greater effort, and show more work commitment (Rathi et al, 2021). However, during a crisis, where flexibility and innovation are crucial, administrators may prefer styles that allow for adaptability. Transactional leadership might prioritize short-term results over long-term individual development. In a health crisis, administrators may lean towards leadership styles that actively support and develop their teams to address evolving challenges. The

top-down decision-making structure of transactional leadership contrasts with the need for collaborative decision-making in a crisis (Kummelstedt, 2023). Democratic and transformational leadership styles, which involve team members, scored higher. Reliance on extrinsic motivators may be a limitation in a crisis where intrinsic motivation is crucial—styles inspiring and engaging teams may be preferred for fostering a shared sense of purpose. Transactional leadership may face challenges in adapting quickly to the rapidly changing circumstances of a health crisis, given its hierarchical structure and emphasis on established procedures. The hierarchical and procedure-bound nature of transactional leadership may pose difficulties in responding to the dynamic and rapidly evolving nature of health crises.

The data shows that *autocratic leadership* was the least favored by school administrators during the health crisis, (WM=2.69; SD=0.7448). The high standard deviation indicates diverse opinions among school administrators about autocratic leadership's appropriateness during the health crisis. Autocratic leadership, marked by top-down decision-making, may be seen as inflexible during the fluid and unpredictable circumstances of a health crisis. This style limits employee participation in decisions.

During a crisis, collaboration and inclusivity, found in democratic or transformational leadership, are preferred for maintaining team morale. Autocratic leadership may lead to resistance and increased stress. In a crisis where uncertainty is high, imposing decisions without considering input can create a negative work environment (San et al., 2021). According to Zhao et al. (2022), autocratic leadership may stifle creativity. Crisis demands novel solutions, favoring leadership styles like democratic or transformational, which involve team members in decision-making and foster creativity. The autocratic style may neglect employee well-being. In a crisis, where health and morale are crucial, leadership styles showing care, like transformational or democratic leadership, are preferred.

The findings suggest that administrators used different styles of leadership, with a strong inclination toward transformational and hands-off leadership styles (Laissez-Faire). In contrast, autocratic leadership is less favored, though it is used highly. Breevaart and Zacher (2019) illustrated that when leaders show both transformational and laissez-faire leadership, subordinates have higher trust in leaders. Organizations may benefit from fostering a leadership culture that aligns with these preferences, promoting loyalty, creativity, and autonomy.

Leaders need to be mindful of these preferences to enhance team engagement and performance. It is important to note that the choice of leadership style during a health crisis can vary based on the specific context, the severity of the crisis, the organizational culture, and the nature of the tasks involved. While the laissez-faire approach may be effective in certain situations, a balanced combination of leadership styles may be more suitable for addressing the multifaceted challenges posed by a health crisis in an educational setting. Administrators should continually assess the effectiveness of their chosen leadership style and be open to adjusting their approach based on the evolving needs of the situation.

Table 1
Respondents' Leadership Styles

Construct	WM	StDev	Interpretation
Transactional	3.34	0.5427	VH
Transformational	3.39	0.5943	VH
Democratic	3.37	0.6594	VH
Laissez-Faire	3.44	0.4604	VH
Autocratic	2.69	0.7448	H

Legend:

3.26-4.00 – Very High (VH)

2.26-3.25 –High (H)

1.26-2.25 – Low (L)

1.00-1.25 – Very Low (VL)

Respondents' Management Skills

Table 2 shows the respondents' management skills. Among the three management skills, the school administrators primarily used conceptual skills during the health crisis, (WM= 0.54 ; SD= 0.4761), which shows that the school administrators frequently used the skills of using intellect in thinking, processing ideas and planning how to manage the health crisis. The school administrators used conceptual skills to find meaning and solutions to the academic institutions' issues and to understand what the school stands for and where it is headed during this time of pandemic where uncertainties keep on evolving. Conceptual skills play a big role in dealing with change, which can be construed from the research study of Jasim (2019), who says that the highest level of leading change in the government sectors in Dubai requires conceptual skills that are essential in achieving the desired change. Conceptual skills are found essential in leading change. Moreover, there are also misconceptions and erroneous conceptual skills by leaders that may prevent the attainment of the desired change. Thus, leaders have to make efforts to conceptually find means to lead subordinates into a smooth transition towards inevitable and essential change.

The school administrators also commonly used interpersonal skills, (WM=3.53; SD=0.5354). Most school administrators constantly use these skills since they are dealing with complexities and uncertainties that vary from work-related conditions, financial constraints, social constraints, and resource limitations to personal life involving physical and mental health threats and one's work. These skills are in concordance with the styles of leadership the school administrators predominantly use in dealing with health crises, which are laissez-faire, democratic, and transformational, all giving consideration to humanness. Human skills are the ability of the manager to work with and through people and work effectively in a group and relate to people, motivate, coordinate, lead, facilitate, communicate, and resolve conflicts (Daft, 2021). Caring is part of humanness, as caring for subordinates means regarding them as valued people as they are concerned with their well-being. The school administrators' acts of finding ways to reach the subordinates and other stakeholders through channels of communication and collaborating with them, being transparent and understanding the diversity of each worker, and understanding the threats and uncertainties of the pandemic brought to the workers are human management skills they used. Flexible forms of work engagement through virtual or online meetings,

transactions, and teaching modalities consider the threats of the pandemic in dealing with workers, students, and parents. The provision of mental health awareness, implementation of health and safety protocols at school, work at home, and other flexible arrangements are applications of human skills by the administrators. Maddox-Daines (2023) emphasized the importance of soft skills and authentic leadership during a pandemic. Tow and Mohammad (2022) found that effective leadership shows that the emotionally intelligent school leader can show empathy, be optimistic, build morale, and motivate.

The technical skills of school administrators scored very high as well, (WM=3.39; SD=0.5429). This data shows that school administrators commonly use these skills to facilitate the transition to digital transactions and online modes of teaching. Being acquainted with, trained in, and applying information and communication technology during a health crisis shows the importance of technical skills in the changing work environment. Providing workers with seminars and training on the use of digital and ICT learning systems and incorporating them into their daily work, as the administrators of schools have been doing, are skills that are indispensable in the new environment brought on by the health crisis. Technology facilitates the sustainability of the institutions since learning relies more on digital technology since the level of integration of ICT and digital technology during the pandemic is high (Manco-Chavez et al., 2020). Rudenko et al. (2020) resolved that there should be a strong emphasis on a comprehensive approach to support students and academic staff in the online learning environment. Training teachers to maintain the quality of teaching in a remote environment was one of the best possible responses the school administrators used in response to the challenges that arose (do Lago et al., 2023). The study of Kesik and Önen (2023) shows that administrators mainly performed technical work and operations related to the smooth implementation of distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Managers, according to Griffin (2021), should have the knowledge of how to perform a task assigned to those they supervise to become effective managers. Hence, the school administrators used very highly all the management skills in terms of conceptual skills, interpersonal skills, and conceptual skills during the pandemic, with conceptual skills as the most frequently used skills. School administrators constantly used these skills to manage schools during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 2
Respondents' Management Skills

Constr5uct	WM	StDev	I
Technical	3.39	0.5429	VH
Interpersonal	3.53	0.5354	VH
Conceptual	3.54	0.4761	VH

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Very High (VH)
2.26-3.25 –High (H)

1.26-2.25 – Low (L)
1.00-1.25 – Very Low (VL)

Respondents' Response to Health Crisis

Table 3 shows the respondents' response to health crisis. Enrolment has the predominant response (WM=3.64; SD=0.4800), which indicates that the school administrators' response to the health crisis focused very highly on the changes in the enrolment system while protecting the stakeholders' health. This is corroborated in the study of Anderson (2021), who accentuated how educational institutions face significant hurdles due to declining enrollment. Since schools have experienced declining enrollments when the pandemic hits (Agoncillo, 2020; Jacobs and Veney, 2022; Toquero, 2020). School administrators find ways to sustain schools, which includes adapting to the new enrollment procedures, protocols, and school promotion strategies to attract enrollees. The use of modern technology, such as the Internet and social media, served as strategies for effective enrollment management (Dei et al., 2023). Changes in the enrollment system led to the sustainability of the school's operation. School administrators find ways to continue the enrollment of students despite health threats by considering other options for the enrollment process and communicating with parents and students to reach them through the established channels of the school to ensure a safe working environment for faculty, staff, and students.

Physical set up and facility changes (WM=3.62; SD= 0.4631) have become the common response of school administrators to health crises since the CHED (2021) mandated schools to comply with the retrofitting of schools when applying for face-to-face classes. The schools change their physical set-up by retrofitting to ensure safety for teachers and students by using masks, putting up barriers, shields, handwashing areas, traffic flows, ventilation, and putting a 1-meter distance from one chair to another. Putting up signage to give warnings or instructions and the strict implementation of health and safety protocols were practiced inside the campus. WHO (2020) attests that physical interventions such as handwashing can help reduce the risk of respiratory infections. Hence, administrators responded very highly to the changes in physical set-up and facility. This result corroborated the study of Navaratnam et al. (2022) that COVID-19 forced changes in the working environment because of the attempt to prevent the spread of infection in workplaces.

Staffing (WM=3.59; SD=0.4992 and teaching modality (WM=3.59; SD=0.4756) constructs were also used very highly by the respondents. The staffing construct includes adjusting staffing schedules, providing access to support such as resources and access to health services, ensuring open lines of communication among them and the school officials, and addressing staffing shortages, which are the responses of school administrators towards the health crisis. Orienting and training the faculty and staff on digital and ICT using new modalities of office transactions and teaching enhances cooperation from them. Training teachers to teach in a remote environment was one of the best responses the school administrators used in response to the challenges that arose (do Lago et al., 2023) since the use of technology facilitates the sustainability of operations during the pandemic (Manco-Chavez et al., 2020). Singh et al. (2021) stressed that it is very important to focus on faculty capacity building to become more familiar with online learning approaches during the pandemic. Mental health services for workers are

also important as emotional distress is ubiquitous among them (Pfefferbaum and North, 2020). Work-from-home arrangements for staff have benefited both the school and the workers. The workers are protected from the virus because it reduces the chance of having COVID-19 infections among workers (Alipour et al., 2021). The study of Moosavi et al. (2022) also highlighted the rescheduling of workers to fit into the changes and issues brought about by the pandemic.

School administrators practiced the use of a new teaching modality, indicating flexibility and adaptability to the new normal. Administrators used online teaching, used channels of communication using technology for student-teacher interaction, and ensured teachers had access to professional development to be used in the teaching and learning process in order to fit the crisis. The study of Heifetz and Linsky (2017) highlighted the significance of adaptive leadership and organizational restructuring in responding to crises and enhancing flexibility in adapting to changes. Hodges et al. (2020) underscored the immediate need to adapt to remote learning during a pandemic. Hence, the private tertiary higher education school administrators in Dipolog City respond to the COVID-19 health crisis by adjusting to the drastic changes brought by it by focusing very much on enrollment, staffing, physical and facility changes, and teaching modality to deliver education to the public while protecting the stakeholders and sustaining school operations.

Table 3
Respondents' Response to Health Crisis

Construct	WM	StDev	I
Enrollment	3.64	0.4800	VH
Staffing	3.59	0.4992	VH
Physical Set-up and facility	3.62	0.4631	VH
Changes	3.59	0.4756	VH
Teaching Modality Used			

Legend: 3.26-4.00 – Very High (VH)
2.26-3.25 –High (H)

1.26-2.25 – Low (L)

1.00-1.25 – Very Low (VL)

Significant Relationship between the Leadership Style Used by the School Administrators and their Response to a Health Crisis

Table 4 shows the significant relationship between the leadership style used by the school administrators and their response to a health crisis. On transactional leadership and response to a health crisis, which are enrollment ($p=0.00$; $r=0.609$), staffing ($p=0.00$; $r=0.601$), physical set-up and teaching ($p=0.00$; $r=0.561$), modality ($p=0.00$; $r=0.543$), shows that the p - values are lower than 0.05. Thus, the null hypotheses must be rejected. Hence, there are significant relationships among them. The r - r -values indicate that in this style of leadership, there are strong correlations between it and the enrollment and staffing responses while the physical set-up and teaching modality used are moderate. In the study of Purwanto (2020), transactional leadership, together with transformational leadership, has positive and significant effects on teachers' ability to innovate during a crisis. This leadership also focuses on developing commitment, passion, and loyalty by

generating new growth ideas and perspectives (Korejan and Shahbazi, 2016). In times of crisis, this type of leadership can help maintain the stability of an organization (Cherry, 2022). Furthermore, Purnomo et al. (2021) found that transactional leadership positively impacted crisis management.

On transformational leadership and response to health crises, which are enrollment ($p=0.00$; $r=0.528$), staffing ($p=0.00$; $r=0.573$), physical set-up and facility changes ($p=0.00$; $r=0.531$), and teaching modality ($p=0.00$; $r=0.521$), shows that the p- values are lower than 0.05, thus there are significant relationships among them. The r- r-values show that there are moderate correlations between this style of leadership and the respondents' responses to health crises. This corroborates the study of Ma and Yang (2020) in China, who found that transformational leadership has a significant correlation with crisis management performance. Mathende and Yousefi (2021) argued that transformational leadership is the most suitable style in challenging environments. The study of Dwidienawati et al. (2021) proved that transformational leadership positively influenced the effectiveness of crisis management. Meanwhile, Al Harbi et al. (2019) showed in their research that there is a significant positive relationship between transformational leadership, followers' creativity, and organizational innovation.

On democratic style of leadership and response to a health crisis, which are enrollment ($p=0.00$; $r=0.593$), staffing ($p=0.00$; $r=0.663$), physical set-up and facility changes ($p=0.00$; $r=0.639$), and teaching modality ($p=0.00$; $r=0.611$), show again that the p- values are lower than 0.05. Thus, the democratic style of leadership has a significant relationship with the school administrators' response to health crises as to enrollment, staffing, physical set-up, and teaching modality. The r-values show that the correlations between democratic leadership and the responses of school administrators to the health crisis are strong. How the administrators respond to health crises is strongly influenced by the style of leadership they have, which is participative leadership. Administrators used this for a unified approach and for flexibility, which is needed during crisis situations. Democratic principles such as equality and freedom of speech improve leadership in times of pandemic (Mncube and Olawale, 2021). Democratic leadership was dominantly used in managing information dissemination during the COVID-19 pandemic (Pounder, 2022). Researchers, however, recommend that school leaders focus on distributive leadership within the organization when facing a crisis such as the pandemic (Fernandez and Shaw, 2020).

The Laissez-Faire styles of leadership and response to a health crisis, namely enrollment ($p=0.00$; $r=0.274$), staffing ($p=0.00$; $r=0.365$), physical set-up and facility changes ($p=0.00$; $r=0.337$), and teaching modality ($p=0.00$; $r=0.365$), also show that the p- values are lower than 0.05. Thus, there are also significant relationships among them. However, there are weak correlations, as can be seen in the r-values, between this style of leadership and the respondents' response to health crisis. Fernandez and Shaw (2020) attest in their research findings that distributive leadership improves the quality of decisions in crisis resolution. The decentralized decision-making of laissez-faire leadership allows for quick response at the local level, which is crucial in a crisis (Kostiainen, 2023). Tong (2020) found that Laissez-Faire psychological leadership has a

positive effect on the learning ability of an organization. Hence, it is good during the COVID-19 pandemic, where drastic transitions to online and blended modalities are needed.

The autocratic style of leadership of the school administrators and their response to a health crisis, which are enrollment ($p=0.00$; $r=0.127$) and physical set-up and facility changes ($p=0.00$; $r=0.092$), show that the p- p-values are lower than 0.05. Thus, the null hypotheses are rejected. Hence, there are significant relationships between them. Whereas the p- p-values of the autocratic style and the staffing ($p=0.437$; $r=0.075$) and teaching modality ($p=0.241$; $r=0.112$) have a higher value than 0.05; thus, the null hypotheses were accepted. Hence, there are no significant relationships between autocratic leadership style and staffing and teaching modality.

The study result shows that there are moderate to strong correlations between the transactional, transformational, and democratic leadership styles used by the school administrators during the COVID-19 health crisis and their response to this pandemic in terms of enrollment, staffing, physical set-up, and facility changes, and teaching modality used. At the same time, there are weak correlations between laissez-faire and response to health crisis. There are no correlations between autocratic leadership and the staffing and teaching modality used by school administrators in response to the pandemic. Only the autocratic leadership did not correlate with the school administrators' response to health crisis in terms of staffing and teaching modality. In contrast, all other respondents' response are related to the style of how they lead the institution.

Hence, the computed data show that there is a connection between the leadership styles that were used by the school administrators in the tertiary private higher educational institutions in Dipolog City and how they respond to the COVID-19 health crisis through enrollment, staffing, physical set-up and facility and teaching modality changes, except for the school administrators use of autocratic leadership's response on staffing and teaching modality, in which there are no significant relationships between autocratic leadership and staffing and autocratic leadership and the teaching modality used by the school administrators. The correlation between leadership styles and response to health crisis corroborated Kapucu and Ustun's research study (2018), which found that leadership competencies have a relationship with the effectiveness of crisis management. While Buhagiar and Anand (2023) stressed that leadership is responsible for management strategies and establishing motivations among employees.

Table 4**Significant Relationship between the Leadership Style Used by the School Administrators and their Response to Health Crisis**

Variables	Enrollment	Staffing	Physical Set-Up	Teaching Modality Used
Transactional	r=0.609 p=0.00** D=Reject Ho	r=0.601 p=0.00** D=Reject Ho	r=0.561 p=0.00** D=Reject Ho	r=0.543 p=0.00** D=Reject Ho
Transformational	r=0.528 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.573 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.531 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.521 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho
Democratic	r=0.593 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.663 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.639 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.611 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho
Laissez-Faire	r=0.274 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.365 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.337 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.365 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho
Autocratic	r=0.127 p=0.00** D=Reject Ho	r=0.075 p=0.437 D= Accept Ho	r=0.092 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.112 p=0.241 D= Accept Ho

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the leadership style used by the school administrators and their response to health crisis.

*Legend: 0.00-0.01**Highly Significant 0.02-0.05*Significant above 0.05 Not Significant*

Significant Relationships between the Management Skills Used by the School Administrators and their Response to Health Crisis

The statistical report shown in table 5 shows the significant relationship between management skills used by the school administrators and their response to a health crisis. The computed data on the relationships between Technical skills and enrollment (p=0.00; r=0.504), staffing (p=0.00; r=0.384), physical set-up and facility changes (p=0.00; r=0.407), and teaching modality (p=0.00; r=0.489) shows the p-values of all these constructs are lower than 0.05. Hence, the null hypotheses are all rejected. Thus, there are significant relationships between the technical skills of school administrators and their response to enrollment, staffing, physical set-up facility changes, and teaching modality.

On the Interpersonal skills, the computed data on the relationships between these skills and enrollment ($p=0.00$; $r=0.533$), staffing ($p=0.00$; $r=0.634$), physical set-up and facility changes ($p=0.00$; $r=0.548$), and teaching modality ($p=0.00$; $r=0.552$) show that the p-values of all these constructs are lower than 0.05. Hence, the null hypotheses are all rejected. Thus, there are significant relationships between the interpersonal skills of school administrators and their response to enrollment, staffing, physical set-up facility changes, and teaching modality. The r-values show that there are moderate correlations between interpersonal skills and enrollment, physical set-up and facility changes, and teaching modality. At the same time, there is a strong correlation between this skill and staffing.

On the relationship between the conceptual skills of the school administrators and the response to a health crisis, the computed data on enrollment ($p=0.00$; $r=0.585$), staffing ($p=0.00$; $r=0.564$), physical set-up and facility changes ($p=0.00$; $r=0.572$), and teaching modality ($p=0.00$; $r=0.597$) shows the p-values of all these constructs are lower than 0.05. Hence, the null hypotheses are all rejected. Thus, there are significant relationships between the conceptual skills of school administrators and their response to enrollment, staffing, physical set-up facility changes, and teaching modality. The r-values show that there are moderate correlations between conceptual skills and enrollment, staffing, physical set-up and facility changes, and teaching modality.

Hence, there are significant relationships between the three (3) management skills, which are the technical skills, interpersonal skills, and conceptual skills, and the school administrators' response to health crisis in terms of enrollment ($p=0.00$), staffing ($p=0.00$), physical set-up and facility changes ($p=0.00$) and teaching modality ($p=0.00$). This denotes that the management skills of school administrators influence how they respond to health crisis. The results corroborate the study of Hu and Liu (2022) that during a health crisis such as the COVID-19 pandemic, coordination structures are needed due to boundary issues, and crisis communication and coordination are essential. Hu and Liu (2022) also emphasized that exploring mechanisms and processes to integrate better the coordination of networks with hierarchical structures during a pandemic is also necessary. Wenzel et al. (2020) stressed that firm innovations during a crisis are an appropriate response to it. This implies that during a health crisis, being flexible by finding ways how to respond positively to changes during the pandemic is appropriate. The adjustment of the staffing schedule, changes in the processes of enrollment, retrofitting of the physical set-up and facility, and shifting from traditional face-to-face classes to blended or online learning classes are appropriate response to the pandemic to sustain school operation. Adjustment to fit into the changes brought by the pandemic is a positive response to it. A web-based solution has been found to fill in the gap in resource allocation during the pandemic (Krausz et al., 2020). Velki and Miočić (2023) stressed that previous experience with Information Communication Technology (ICT) was crucial for teachers to shift successfully to an online learning modality.

Hence, the computed data show how the school administrators manage the schools using their technical, conceptual, and technical skills influences how they respond to the health

crisis in terms of enrollment, staffing, physical set-up and facility changes, and the teaching modality they use during the health crisis, specifically the COVID-19 pandemic.

Table 5
Significant Relationship between the Management Skills Used by the School Administrators and their Response to Health Crisis

Variables	Enrollment	Staffing	Physical and Set-Up and Facility Changes	Teaching Modality Used
Technical	r=0.504 p=0.00** D=Reject Ho	r=0.384 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.407 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.489 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho
Interpersonal	r=0.533 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.634 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.548 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.552 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho
Conceptual	r=0.585 p=0.00**	r=0.564 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.572 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho	r=0.597 p=0.00** D= Reject Ho

Ho: There is no significant relationship between the management skills used by the school administrators and their response to health crisis.

Legend: 0.00-0.01**Highly Significant 0.02-0.05*Significant above 0.05 Not Significant

Predictors of School Administrators' Response to Health Crisis

Table 6 presented, transactional leadership, democratic leadership, and conceptual management skills were identified as predictors of school administrators' response to health crisis. These findings suggest that a combination of Transactional, Democratic leadership styles and Conceptual management skills contributes significantly to school administrators' effective response to the health crisis. School administrators who exhibited a *transactional leadership* (0.1728) style are associated with a positive response to the health crisis. Transactional leaders focus on tasks, clarify roles and responsibilities, and provide rewards for meeting expectations. In a crisis, this style may ensure efficient coordination and execution of necessary tasks.

The positive coefficient for the *Democratic leadership* (0.1924) style suggests that administrators who involve stakeholders in decision-making (such as teachers, parents, and students) are more likely to respond effectively to health crises. Collaboration and shared decision-making can enhance communication and garner support during

challenging times. Mncube and Olawale (2021) stressed that the principles of democratic leadership, such as equality and freedom of speech, enhance leadership in times of pandemic. The highest coefficient is associated with *Conceptual Management skills*. Administrators with a conceptual orientation focus on long-term vision and innovation. This suggests that administrators who emphasize strategic thinking and innovative approaches are more likely to respond effectively to health crises, possibly by adapting to changing circumstances and proactively addressing emerging challenges.

The study found that Transactional and Democratic leadership styles and Conceptual management skills play a significant role in shaping administrators' response during the health crisis. The Adjusted R-squared stands at 46.86%, indicating the model's explanatory strength while considering the potential complexity arising from the inclusion of various leadership dimensions. The Predicted R-squared stands at 44.31%, indicating the model's effectiveness in forecasting future response. The highest coefficient associated with the Conceptual leadership style signifies the pivotal role of visionary thinking and innovation in responding proactively to health crises. Relevant literature on crisis leadership styles in healthcare includes distributed and adaptive leadership styles, transformational, servant, transactional, autocratic, and charismatic leadership styles, and democratic, consultative, and authoritarian leadership styles (Buscema et al., 2023; Bourgeault et al., 2020; Smithson 2022; Wu et al., 2021).

The interplay of Transactional, Democratic, and Conceptual leadership styles significantly influences administrators' response to the health crisis. The Adjusted R-squared provides a nuanced understanding of the model's explanatory power, accounting for the complexities introduced by multiple predictors. The Predicted R-squared underscores the practical utility of the model, suggesting its effectiveness in forecasting administrators' reactions. These insights contribute to a more comprehensive understanding of the dynamics influencing effective crisis response strategies in educational leadership.

Schools may prioritize developing leadership styles and management skills through training programs. This includes improving channels and modes of communication, encouraging collaborative actions and decision-making, and fostering innovation among school administrators and stakeholders. By doing so, schools can better prepare for a health crisis that may occur again, affecting the school and stakeholders. A health crisis plan that ensures the well-being of the stakeholders and community and maintains education continuity may be an effective response to a health crisis.

Table 6
Predictors of School Administrators' Response to Health Crisis

Term	Coef	SE Coef	T-Value	P-Value
Constant	1.104	0.273	4.05	0.00
Transactional	0.1728	0.0862	2.00	0.04
Democratic	0.1924	0.0779	2.47	0.01

Conceptual	0.3560	0.0851	4.18	0.00
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Model Summary

S	R-sq	R-sq (adj)	R-sq(pred)
0.346678	48.31%	46.86%	44.31%

Regression Equation

Teaching Modality Used = 1.104 + 0.1728 Transactional + 0.1924 Democratic + 0.3560 Conceptual

Ho: There are no predictors of school administrators' response

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. The school administrators in the private tertiary education in Dipolog City, Philippines used various styles of leadership during a health crisis. They predominantly used laissez-faire leadership. Since the pandemic situation is a new and strange kind of crisis, a laissez-faire approach allows quick decisions based on expertise and local conditions in responding to this crisis.
2. The school administrators frequently used conceptual, interpersonal, and technical skills in responding to the health crisis. These management skills made the school administrators adjust to the new normal successfully.
3. The school administrators focused very highly on enrollment, staffing, physical set-up facility changes, and teaching modality used. Most school administrators focused very highly on responding to enrolment in order to sustain school operations.
4. There are significant relationships between all administrators' leadership styles and their responses to health crisis in enrolment and physical set-up and facility changes. There are significant relationships between all leadership styles, except autocratic and their responses to the crisis in terms of the staffing and teaching modality used. Hence, only autocratic leadership did not correlate with the school administrators' responses in terms of staffing and teaching modality. In contrast, all other respondents' responses correlated to the style of how they lead the institution.
5. There are significant relationships between the administrators' management skills and their responses to health crisis, such as the COVID-19 pandemic.
6. Transactional leadership, Democratic leadership, and Conceptual management skills are identified as predictors of school administrators' response to COVID-19 health crisis. Hence, they played a significant role in shaping administrators' response during the health crisis.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, the following are the recommendations:

1. School administrators may use the style of leadership and management skills that are contingent on the situation; thus, exploring crisis situations is needed before responding to the crisis may be employed.
2. School administrators may strengthen the support system by establishing sectoral linkages through communication and collaboration. Other academic and related agencies may showcase best academic practices, which serve as guides for school administrators in leading and managing a school.
3. School administrators may become technologically abreast to facilitate technological innovation to enhance teaching modality in response to any crisis that may happen again.
4. School administrators may formulate a crisis response plan that includes innovative transactions and teaching modalities to sustain school operations and maintain students' learning engagement.
5. Collaboration and communication between school administrators and stakeholders are necessary to sustain operations. Communicating with stakeholders on issues and plans of the school may elucidate concerns and foster cooperation from stakeholders.
6. School administrators may become abreast of new approaches to leadership and management in preparation for any future crisis.
7. Further research may be done on leadership and management among school leaders, focusing on another kind of health crisis situation in bigger and different settings for comparative data and outcomes. Researchers may also conduct a study on the use of laissez-faire leadership in health crises and its positive impacts on organizations.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This research adhered to the ethical standards of research. It sought approval from institutional review board authorities, voluntary participation of the respondents were sought, and informed consent was secured. The respondents voluntarily participated in the study and were given the right to ask questions if they needed clarifications pertaining to the research. They were informed that they have the right to refuse and withdraw from participating in the research at any time they want. The safety and security of the respondents were ensured, and no harm happened to them or they were at health risk during the conduct of the research. The respondents were protected from physical, social, and economic risks while participating in the research. The respondents were also informed of what to be done in this research, and how the data would be gathered, and discussed with them the purpose of the research. The researcher ensured the anonymity and confidentiality of the respondents observing the data privacy law. The data findings were kept well and used for this study alone, but they were discarded after the research was done. Moreover, the research was done with honesty and transparency; plagiarism

was avoided, and no conflict of interest existed in the conduct of the research. Misleading information and representation of data findings were also avoided.

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